

Table S1. Sequence of primers used in construction of plasmids.

Gene	Sequence 5'- 3'
WT-DDX24	F <u>GAAGATCTGCCACCATGAAGTTGAAGGACACAAA</u>
	R <u>CCCAAGCTTGTGATGGTGATGGTGATGGCCCTGAAAATACAGGT</u>
K11E-DDX24	F AAGGACACAAAATCAAGGCCAGAGCAGTCAAGCTGTGGCAAA
	R TTTGCCACAGCTTGACTGCTCTGGCCTTGATTTTGTGTCCTT
E271K-DDX24	F CTCCTCCAAGTAACACCAAAGCACCTGGAGAGA
	R TCTCTCCAGGTGGTGCTTTGGTGTTACTTGGAGGAG

Figure S2